

Studies on Quinoline Derivatives. Preparation and Anti-microbial Activity of N^1 -(2-Aryl/Styryl-6-acetylquinolino)- N^3 -arylureas/thioureas/ N^4 -H-arylthiosemicarbazides

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Quinolines¹ as well as ureas, thioureas and thiosemicarbazides² possess various biological activities. In view of this, it was proposed to synthesise some new ureas, thioureas and thiosemicarbazides of 2-aryl/styryl-6-acetylquinoline-4-carboxylic acid (3) according to Scheme 1. The structures of the compounds have been established by elemental analy-

ses, ir and pmr spectral data. The compounds have been evaluated for antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Hitachi R-1200 spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal reference.

N^1 -2-(Phenyl-6-acetylquinolino-4-yl)- N^3 -phenylurea/thiourea/thiosemicarbazide (3): A mixture of 2-phenyl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline³ (1) (1.45 g, 0.005 mol) in dioxane (40 ml) and thionyl chloride (10 ml) was refluxed at 60–70° for 3 h. Excess of thionylchloride was then removed by distillation and the product (2) obtained was refluxed with phenylurea (1.36 g, 0.01 mol)/phenylthiourea (1.52 g, 0.01 mol)/thiosemicarbazide (0.91 g, 0.01 mol) using dioxane (15 ml) as solvent for 6 h. The contents were then poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol. Physical and spectral data of the compounds (yields 40–67%) are recorded in Table 1.

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS (3)*

Sl no **	R	R'	M P °C
	X = NHCO-NHR'		
1	Phenyl	Phenyl	99
2	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	181
3	Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	202

Table 1 (contd.)							
4.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	116	46.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	121
5.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	191	47.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	222
6.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	179	48.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	183
7.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	49.	3-[Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	202
8.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	192	50.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	245
9.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	30	51.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	199
10.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	195	52.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	164
11.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	208	53.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	195
12.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	186	54.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	181
13.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	179	55.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	224
14.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	150	56.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	215
15.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	193	57.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	199
16.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	244	58.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	166
17.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	252	59.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	181
18.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	300	60.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	217
19.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	280	61.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	240
20.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	202	62.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	170
21.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	184	63.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	187
22.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	216	64.	Styryl	Phenyl	204
23.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	283	65.	Styryl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	224
24.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	224	66.	Styryl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	210
25.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	221	67.	Styryl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	182
26.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	300	68.	Styryl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	296
27.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	218	69.	Styryl	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	255
28.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	168	70.	Styryl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	186
29.	Styryl	Phenyl	199	X = NHCS-NHNHR'			260
30.	Styryl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	210	71.	Phenyl	H	250
31.	Styryl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	173	72.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	H	330
32.	Styryl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	187	73.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	248
33.	Styryl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	210	74.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	320
34.	Styryl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	178	75.	Styryl	H	186
35.	Styryl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	197	76.	Phenyl	Phenyl	191
36.	Phenyl	Phenyl	189	77.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	H	219
37.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	113	78.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	248
38.	Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	274	79.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	236
39.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	172	80.	Styryl	H	162
40.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	198	81.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	165
41.	Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	171	82.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	317
42.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	183	83.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	322
43.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	183	84.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	320
44.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	192	85.	Styryl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	207
45.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	255	86.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	261
				87.	3-Methoxy- 4-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	

Table 1 (contd)

88	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	300
89	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	266
90	Styryl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	160

* All compound gave satisfactory N analysis.

** Compd. sl. no. 1 : ν_{\max} 3 350 (NH), 3 020 (CH Q-ring), 1 685 (CH₃CO), 1 665 (NH-C), 1 580, 1 480 (C=C + C=N Q-ring), 1 358 (CH str. of CH₃); δ 2.6 1 (3H, s, CH₃C=O), 7.22–8.05 (10H, m, ArH + Q-3H), 9.98 (1H, s, NH), 10.34 (1H, s, ArNH), 10.50 (1H, s, OH-enolic); sl. no. 36 : ν_{\max} 3 450, 3 240, 3 120 (NH), 3 025 (CH Q-ring), 1 685 (CH₃C-O), 1 600 (NH bend), 1 580, 1 480 (C=C + C=N Q-ring), 1 360 (CH of CH₃), 1 220, 1 190 (C=S); δ 2.65 (3H, s, CH₃C=O), 7.15–8.10 (10H, m, ArH + Q-3H), 9.95 (2H, s, Q-NH), 10.31 (1H, s, ArNH); sl. no. 71 : 3 445, 3 235, 3 125 (NH), 3 035 (CH str. of Q-ring), 1 680 (CH₃C=O), 1 610 (NH bend), 1 575, 1 465 (C=C + C=N of Q-ring), 1 365 (CH of CH₃), 1 230, 1 200 (C=S); δ 2.59 (3H, s, CH₃C=O), 7.09–8.01 (13H, ArH), 8.05 (1H, s, Q-8), 9.94 (1H, s, NH), 10.2 (1H, s, NH-C), 10.39 (1H, s, ArNH).

Antimicrobial activity : All the compounds (3) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *B. mega* and *E. coli* by cup-plate⁴ method at a concentration of 50 μ g using DMF as solvent. After 24 h of incubation at 37^o, the zones of inhibition were measured in mm. The activity was compared with known antibiotics i.e. Ampicillin (*S. aureus*, 21; *B. mega*, 27; *E. coli*, 25), Chloramphenicol (*S. aureus*, 28; *B. mega*, 20; *E. coli*,

21), Norfloxacin (*S. aureus*, 22; *B. mega*, 20 ; *E. coli*, 19 mm). All the compounds showed moderate to good antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (12–22 mm), *B. mega* (12–20 mm), *E. coli* (10–19 mm zone of inhibition) at same concentration.

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